

Free Particle Quantum Mechanics From the Relationship Between $F=dp/dt$ and Special Relativity?

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It is well-known that special relativity and $F=dp/dt$ are closely related. In fact, the latter holds in Newtonian mechanics, but also in special relativity if one uses $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ (one dimension here). We suggest that one may find the relations $dx=\hbar/p$ and $dt=\hbar/E$ from this relationship. In other words, we suggest that one may think of $p/\Delta t$ and $E/\Delta x$ as average constant forces (i.e. p changes linearly in t and E in x , with E representing both inertia and v effects). This follows as a generalization of the consideration of a frame moving with $-dv$. If one has constant forces, this may be seen as an average and one may postulate that one has in fact probabilistic force delivery leading to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ as a probability in x,t .

Newtonian Mechanics

In Newtonian mechanics, a rest mass, m_0 , may be thought of as an inertia which is then thought of in terms of a force required to move the rest mass. Rest mass is thus associated with force. If a rest mass is viewed from a frame moving with constant $-v$, then it is seen to move with v . It now has energy $E=m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and momentum $p=m_0v/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, and we argue that both should be associated with force. Physically, this seems reasonable because both are part of a 4-vector and an object with momentum exerts a force when striking a target. We wish, however, to quantify this situation. Before doing so, we consider the Newtonian case;

$$F=dp/dt = m_0 dv/dt \quad \text{and} \quad d/dx (.5m_0vv) = m_0 v dv/dx = m_0 dv/dt \quad ((1))$$

We see how dp/dt or $d(\text{kinetic energy})/dx$ both yield force if one involves derivatives, i.e. dx and dt . This, we argue, suggests a link between E,p and spacetime intervals dx and dt , which we try to develop.

Lorentz Invariant $-Et+px$ And $F=dp/dt$

We consider the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et'+px' = -m_0cc^2 t \quad ((2))$$

Consider a particle at rest at $x=0$ at t with m_0 and then consider a frame moving with constant $-dv$. In such a case,

$$p \rightarrow dp \quad (\text{as it is proportional to } dv) \quad \text{and} \quad E' \rightarrow m_0cc^2 + dE(dv) \quad ((3))$$

This allows one to consider ((2)) as

$$-dE' dt' + dp' dx' = 0 \quad ((3))$$

Here $t' = 1/\sqrt{1-dv/dv/cc} t$ and so $t'=t$ to first order in dv .

t' and x' are intervals measured from 0,0 and so we use dt' and dx' . If one then divides ((3)) by $dx'dt'$ then one has:

$$-dE'/dx' + dp'/dt' = 0 \quad ((4))$$

((4)) follows from a Lorentz invariant, but holds for all points on an $x'=vt'$ trajectory. $dp'/dt' = F$ from Newtonian mechanics and so dE'/dx' must also be force as the two terms are subtracted. To test this is special relativity, consider: (here we use x' and x interchangeably)

$$dE'/dx = d/dx (mocc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}) = E'/(1-vv/cc) dv/dt \quad ((5a)) \text{ and}$$

$$dp'/dt = d/dt (mov/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}) = E'/cc dv/dt \quad ((5b))$$

The two are the same, and $dp/dt = F$ also holds in special relativity.

We considered ((3)) for a small dv . In such a case,

$$dt' = hbar / (E'(dv)-mocc) \quad \text{and} \quad dx' = hbar / p'(dv) \quad ((6))$$

One may argue, however, that this notion holds in all frames, not just for dv . This would then lead to:

$$dx = hbar/p \quad ((7)),$$

((7)) is a general dx value which would hold in general. It would even still hold that $\text{Force} = dp/dt$ if p changed linearly in time even for a long time.

but there would issues for E as:

$$-E dt + p dx = -mocc dt \quad ((7))$$

Instead of considering $E-mocc$, one may introduce $dt = hbar/E$ which together with $p \rightarrow 0$ and $dx \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ introduces a kind of symmetry. Now pdx divided by $dxdt$ (with each of these being large numbers now for a general p), then given that:

$$dt = hbar/E \text{ yields } E dt = p dx, \text{ then } E/\Delta x = \text{force}. \quad ((8))$$

Thus, the entire E is being used in $E/\Delta x = \text{Force}$ and not infinitesimals, i.e. a change from $mocc$. In other words, E is linked to force due to inertia as well as the change in v .

This simply means that one must interpret dt in a proper manner. Given that it is strictly linked to E and not to E' and m_{occ} means that it is linked to an entire energy which is more than simply the change $E' - m_{occ}$. This force is equated with $p / \Delta t$.

As a result, we suggest that considerations of special relativity together with $F=dp/dt$ lead to the notion of:

$$dx = \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad dt = \hbar/E \quad ((9))$$

One immediately sees that dx/dt is not velocity (unless one deals with a photon which has rest mass of m_0). Here we specifically deal with particles with rest mass.

As a result, one must provide a physical interpretation for dx and dt as they do not measure motion in space-time. From $dp/dt=F$, one sees that dt is the amount of time required to change the momentum of the particle. ((9)) yields a constant value for this time and so numerically it must be close to 0 for momenta in Newtonian systems.

Given

$\hbar = 1.05 \times 10^{-34} \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}$ one may see that for 1 gram to 1 kg and $v=500 \text{ m/s}$ one has a tiny dx . As a result, dx is negligible in the classical world.

At this point, there is no notion of probability. The idea, however, of a constant force accelerating a particle, however, seems to be an average concept. This suggests that one may use dx and dt as intervals and argue that there is a probability to find an x or t value within the interval. If there is a probability, then there must be a probabilistic physical scenario. We have suggested in previous notes that one may consider elastic scattering. If one has an initial e_1, e_2 and p_1, p_2 (one dimensional vectors) and argues that any outcome $e_i + e_j = e_1 + e_2$ and $p_i + p_j = p_1 + p_2$ has the same product probability, then:

$$\text{Probability} = \exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad ((10))$$

in order to be Lorentz invariant. This then leads to free particle quantum mechanics. Thus, there is a dx spatial range linked with probabilistic x values in the interval and a dt temporal range, linked with probabilities in time in the interval.

Composite Systems

In the above discussion, we argued that there exist intervals in x and t linked with p and E . It is possible to have a system like a gas in a tiny container (thought experiment) such that there is a net momentum p , but each sub-particle has its own p . In the above discussion we considered $F=dp/dt$, but if a system has structure, then even though one may write a general $dp/dt=F$ acting on the center-of-mass, there are also torques occurring and one cannot analyze the system solely $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. For example, a tiny gas in equilibrium differs in an interaction from one in which all of the particles are close to one wall if there is any angular feature to the interaction. As a result, the spatial $\exp(ipx)$ is fine for a point-like particle, but for a composite system the

interaction would be more complicated. One must consider various torques and rotational motion and in general such a composite system would change in time even quantum mechanically if the tiny gas is not in equilibrium. A full description would require $Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi)$ s, i.e. a detailed description of the interaction. As an example, one may consider a quantum bound state which has its own internal wavefunction $W(x)$ even though the system may be translating as a whole and there might be a factor $\exp(i p_{cm} x_{cm})$. The factor $\exp(i p_{cm} x_{cm})$ does not describe the full spatial effect as it did for a point particle. Thus, superpositions of $\exp(ipx)$ s become more complicated than the simple $\exp(ipx)$ form.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Newton's second law $dp/dt = \text{Force}$, which holds relativistically if $p = \gamma m v$ may be linked with the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px = -m_0 c^2 t$. As a first step, we consider v being dv so that p is really dp and $E(v) = \gamma m_0 c^2 + dE(v)$ to first order in dv . If one considers $t' = t$ to first order in dv , then one has $-dE/dt + dp/dx = 0$ and dividing by dx yields $-dE/dx + dp/dt = 0$. $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ and so dE/dx must also be force. We then note that one may consider a more general case of $-E/dt + p/dx = 0$. Here dx, dt do not lead to $dx/dt = v$ and E is not dE , but the full energy. In the rest frame, $m_0 c^2$ represents inertial force and so there is more force present than just that linked with dp/dt . One may introduce $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$ which are fixed intervals for a given E, p . We show that they are tiny in a classical world. One may then consider p/dt as a kind of force if p changes linearly in time from $p=0$ and $E/\Delta x$ is a force linked with E changing from 0 to E linearly in x .

One may postulate that one has fixed average forces $E/\Delta x$ and $p/\Delta t$, where $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$. These seem to represent average forces as force most likely does not act in a linear manner. One may then suggest that dt and dx are intervals linked with probabilistic force and so seek a probability. We suggest that the probability chosen should be one which allows equal product probability for any e_i, e_j, p_i, p_k given e_1, e_2, p_1, p_2 (one dimension vector) initial state and $e_i + e_j = e_1 + e_2$ and $p_i + p_j = p_1 + p_2$. This leads to $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ to have Lorentz invariance.